

INTERACTION OF AROMATIC HYDROXYKETONES AND THEIR
DERIVATIVES WITH THIONYL CHLORIDE IN PRESENCE OF
FINELY DIVIDED COPPER. PREPARATION OF 3:3'-DIPRO-
PIONYL-4:6-4':6'-TETRAHYDROXYDIPHENYL THIOETHER
AND ITS DERIVATIVES FROM RESPROPIOPHENONE *

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Preparation of 3:3'-dipropionyl-4:6-4':6'-tetrahydroxydiphenyl thioether and of diacetoxy di-methoxy, tetra-acetoxy and tetramethoxy derivatives of the thioether are described. Nitration, bromination as well as 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of the tetrahydroxy thioether are described.

The present work is the continuation of the work of Jadhav and Merchant (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 265). The reaction was carried out in presence of dry chloroform at room temperature, when the thioether was obtained. Its constitution was arrived at by the action of nitric acid below 5° on it, when 5-nitrorespropiophenone was obtained which showed that the two nuclei were linked through sulphur atom in the position *para* to -OH group and *meta* to -COEt group.

Bromination of the thioether in acetic acid medium furnished a dibromo derivative which on nitration in acetic acid medium afforded 3-bromo-5-nitrorespropiophenone. With excess of liquid bromine, the thioether afforded 2:4:6-tribromoresorcinol, which showed that liquid bromine broke the sulphur linking, oxidised the ketonic group to carboxyl group which ultimately lost carbon dioxide; the resulting resorcinol was brominated.

Diacetoxy, tetra-acetoxy, dimethoxy and tetramethoxy derivatives as well as 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of the thioether were prepared.

The mechanism of the reaction can be explained after Hirwe, Jadhav and Chakradeo (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 101), as the same thioether is also formed by the interaction of sulphur monochloride or sulphur dichloride and the ketone.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

3:3'-Dipropionyl-4:6-4':6'-tetrahydroxydiphenyl Thioether (I).—Respropiophenone (12 g.) was suspended in dry chloroform (80 c.c.) and thionyl chloride (12 c.c.) was added to it, followed by gradual addition of finely divided copper (8 g., 1 hour) and left overnight at room temperature. The solution was filtered and the residue was repeatedly washed with dry chloroform. Brownish red paste, left over after removal of the chloroform at room temperature, was boiled with water for 1 hour. The dark red semi-solid obtained was first crystallised from acetic acid and then from benzene in pinkish white needles, m.p. 161-62°, yield 4 g. (Found: C, 59.5; H, 5.25; S, 8.7. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4S$ requires C, 59.7; H, 4.97; S, 8.8 per cent).

* This communication is to be treated as Part VI of this series.

It developed a red coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution and it dissolved in dilute NaOH solution with a yellow colour. It is easily soluble in acetone, moderately so in benzene, chloroform and acetic acid, and very sparingly in petroleum ether.

The same thioether was obtained by the interaction of the ketone (3 g.) and sulphur monochloride (1 c.c.) or sulphur dichloride (1.5 c.c.) in presence of dry ether (40 c.c.), the addition being done below 5° and allowing the reaction to proceed for 1 hour at room temperature, the yield being 0.3 g. and 0.7 g. respectively.

3:3'-Dipropionyl-4:4'-dihydroxy-6:6'-diacetoxydiphenyl thioether separated out when pyridine (1 c.c.) was added to the hot solution of the thioether (I, 1 g.) in acetic anhydride (10 c.c.). It crystallised in colorless needles from acetic acid, m.p. 216-17° (Found: S, 7.1. $C_{22}H_{22}O_6S$ requires S, 7.2 per cent).

It gave a bottle-green coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution and dissolved in dilute alkali with a yellow colour.

If the above reaction mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath, instead of allowing it to cool, for 1 hour and then poured into dilute HCl and ice mixture, 3:3'-dipropionyl-4:6-4':6'-tetra-acetoxydiphenyl thioether was obtained, crystallising from rectified spirit in colorless needles, m.p. 125-26°. (Found: S, 5.9. $C_{26}H_{26}O_{10}S$ requires S, 6.04 per cent).

It was insoluble in alkali and developed no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution.

3:3'-Dipropionyl-4:4'-dihydroxy-6:6'-dimethoxydiphenyl thioether (II) was prepared by methylating (I) with dimethyl sulphate (1:1) in presence of alkali at 100°. It crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow plates, m.p. 202-203°. (Found: S, 8.5. $C_{26}H_{22}O_6S$ requires S, 8.2 per cent).

It developed a bottle-green coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride and dissolved in dilute alkali with a yellow colour.

Methylation with excess of dimethyl sulphate under similar conditions afforded 3:3'-dipropionyl-4:6-4':6'-tetramethoxydiphenyl thioether. It crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 197-98°. (Found: S, 7.5. $C_{22}H_{26}O_6S$ requires S, 7.6 per cent).

The thioether (II) was also obtained by the interaction of thiouyl chloride (3 c.c.) and copper powder (2 g.) and 2-hydroxy-4-methoxypropiophenone (3.6 g.) at room temperature (yield 1.5 g.) and also by the action of sulphur monochloride (1 c.c.) or sulphur dichloride (1.5 c.c.) in presence of dry ether (50 c.c.) on 2-hydroxy-4-methoxypropiophenone with 0.5 g. and 1 g. yield respectively; in all cases the reaction was allowed to proceed overnight at room temperature.

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones of (I) crystallised from acetic acid in dark red shining plates, m.p. 270° (decomp.). (Found: N, 15.6. $C_{20}H_{22}O_{12}N_2S$ requires N, 15.5 per cent).

2:4-Dihydroxy-5-nitropropiophenone.—The thioether (I, 1 g.) was gradually added to nitric acid (d 1.4, 10 c.c.) at about 5° and the reaction was allowed to proceed at that temperature for about 2 hours. The solid, obtained on diluting the reaction mixture with ice, crystallised from dilute alcohol in white needles, m.p. 131°. No depression in melting point was observed when mixed with an authentic specimen.

3:3'-Dipropionyl-4:6:4':6'-tetrahydroxy-5:5'-dibromodiphenyl Thioether (III).—To the hot solution of the thioether (I, 3.5 g.) in acetic acid (25 c.c.) bromine solution in acetic acid (33 c.c., 10% w/v) was added. On cooling, the bromo derivative separated which crystallised from acetic acid in colorless needles, m.p. 212-113°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: Br, 30.7. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8Br_2S$ requires Br, 30.8 per cent).

3-Bromo-5-nitrorespropiofenone.—The thioether (III, 0.5 g.) was mixed with nitric acid (d 1.4, 2.5 c.c.) at about 5°. It was then heated for about 2 hours on a boiling water-bath and then diluted. The solid obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in colorless needles, m.p. 230-31°. (Found: Br, 27.5. $C_9H_8O_6NBr$ requires Br, 27.6 per cent).

Bromination of 5-nitrorespropiofenone (1 g.) in acetic acid with 8 c.c. of 10% bromine solution furnished the same product.

2:4:6-Tribromoresorcinol.—The thioether (I, 1 g.) was added to liquid bromine (5 c.c.) when it went into solution. Excess of bromine was removed next day and the solid obtained was washed with sodium bisulphite and crystallised from hot water, m.p. 111-112°. Mixed melting point with an authentic specimen, prepared according to Benedikt (*Monatsh.*, 1883, **4**, 227) showed no lowering.

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